

strong aya

A new, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for Adolescents and Young Adults with cancer.

The future of cancer therapy

Deliverable Report

WP4 – Operation of STRONG-AYA ecosystem, stakeholder and patient involvement, dissemination, exploitation, communication

Deliverable D4.7

Operational plans for the pan-European umbrella ecosystem

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Project:	STRONG-AYA
Lead Contributor	Oana Lindner (UOL)
Email	d.p.stark@leeds.ac.uk
Other Contributors	Dan Stark, Oana Lindner, Emily Connearn, Richard Feltbower, Nicola Hughes (UOL); Nicole Collaco (UOS); Leonard Wee, Marine Jacquemin, Joshi Hogenboom, Flora Lysen, Darian Meacham (UNIMAAS); Simone Hanebaum (NKI); Urska Kosir (PAB).
Emails	o.c.lindner@leeds.ac.uk ; e.connearn@leeds.ac.uk ; r.g.feltbower@leeds.ac.uk ; n.f.hughes@leeds.ac.uk ; n.b.collaco@soton.ac.uk ; leonard.wee@maastro.nl ; marine.jacquemin@maastro.nl ; joshi.hogenboom@maastro.nl ; f.lysen@maastrichtuniversity.nl ; d.meacham@maastrichtuniversity.nl ; s.hanebaum@nki.nl ; urska.kosir29@gmail.com .

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Description:

Operational plan containing description of main actions required for the deployment and functioning of the pan-European ecosystem

5. Publishable summary (max ½ page)

This deliverable defines the context and rationale for the existence of the pan-European ecosystem, its governance model (structure, guiding principles, incentives of partners), specific operations, and rules of its operational activities as a pan-European federated learning ecosystem (for ongoing and new members, for the submission of use cases and use of federated analysis infrastructures). These aspects define the path to generating value, insights, impact, and sustainability through collaboration and federated learning, with iterative tailoring to the stakeholders within the STRONG-AYA Consortium.

This deliverable is part of WP4, defining the actions that all institutions need to fulfil for the operation of a sustainable pan-European STRONG-AYA ecosystem. It builds upon the existing national/local ecosystems within STRONG-AYA and previous documents produced within the Consortium related to the architecture of the ecosystem (D2.1), code of conduct of members (D2.2), data management (D3.1), technical blueprint (D3.3), previously-defined local operational plans (D4.4, D4.6) and definition of use cases (D4.8), and key performance indicators (D5.2). Apart from these documents, which all partners are aware of, the current report should be read in conjunction with the ROPA/DPIA and Grant agreement for any additional details.

Details encompassed by the actions defined within the overarching national ecosystem operational plan (D4.4) and operational plans for national ecosystems (D4.6) feed directly into this document, which brings together the actions and operations for the development of national infrastructures feeding into our pan-European umbrella ecosystem. D4.4 and D4.6 both rely on interviews and discussions with each national partner, evaluating the state of preparedness to build from local to national ecosystems. The pan-European ecosystem described here is reliant on each local centre working nationally, to create capacity to build towards a population-based national StSTRONG-AYA ecosystem, which can communicate with other nations.

Consistent with the other deliverables to which this report is linked, it aims to be a living document, developed iteratively throughout the project and beyond. It will evolve as new partners and interested stakeholders may join the Consortium, may contribute data, and the landscape of governance, ethics, and security changes in time at international levels.

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7. Definitions

STRONG AYA consortium members are referred to as following within this text:

1. **NKI-AVL** – Stichting het Nederlands Kanker Instituut – Antoni van Leeuwenhoek Ziekenhuis (NL)
 2. **YCE** – Youth Cancer Europe (RO)
 3. **INT** – Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale dei Tumori (IT)
 4. **FFUND** – FFUND BV (NL)
 5. **CLB** – Centre de Lutte Contre le Cancer Leon Berard (FR)
 6. **ECO** – European Cancer Organisation (BE)
 7. **UNIMAAS** – Universiteit Maastricht (NL)
 8. **IKNL** – Stichting Integraal Kankercentrum Nederland (NL)
 9. **EORTC** – European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer AISBL (BE)
 10. **IGR** – Institut Gustave Roussy (FR)
 11. **MSCNRIO** – Narodowy Instytut Onkologii im. Marii Skłodowskiej-Curie – Państwowy Instytut Badawczy (Marie Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology) (PL)
 12. **UOM** – University of Manchester (UK)
 13. **UOL** – University of Leeds (UK)
 14. **LTHT** – Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust (UL)
 15. **SOUTHAMPTON** – University of Southampton (UK)
- **Grant Agreement** (including its annexes and amendments): the agreement signed between the beneficiaries of the HORIZON Research and Innovations Actions (hereafter referred to as Horizon) and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (hereafter referred to as HADEA) for the undertaking of the STRONG AYA project (Grant Agreement no. 101057482).
 - **Beneficiary**: Signatories of the Grant Agreement
 - **Associated Partner**: Entities which participate in the action but without the right to charge costs or claim contributions.
 - **Project**: the sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
 - **Consortium**: the STRONG AYA consortium, including all the aforementioned partners.
 - **Consortium Agreement**: The agreement made between STRONG AYA members for the implementation and execution of the action outlined in the Grant Agreement. The agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to HADEA on behalf of the European Union, and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

8. Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
AYA	Adolescent and Young Adult
HCP	Health Care Provider
PRO	Patient Reported Outcome
PROM	Patient Reported Outcome Measure
CfC	Committee for Coordination
COS	Core Outcome Set
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FL	Federated learning
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
MDW	Medical Data Works
PHT	Personal Health Train
PI	Principal Investigator
PLUTO	Public Value Assessment Tool
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Lead(s)
WP1	Work Package 1 (Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer & data collection)
WP2	Work Package 2 (Governance, Data Security and Ethics)
WP3	Work Package 3 (Infrastructure and Interoperability)
WP4	Work Package 4 (Operation of STRONG AYA ecosystems, stakeholder and patient involvement, dissemination, exploitation, communication)
WP5	Work Package 5 (Scientific coordination and project management)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OA	Open Access
PAB	Patient Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency

9. 4. Executive summary

1. AYA cancers are rare but can be disabling for a large proportion of surviving young people; moreover, clinical and psychosocial research and care for AYA is not evenly distributed and developed across Europe.
2. Because they are rare, conducting adequately powered research that improves clinical and psychosocial care, and implementing research findings, while meeting young people where they are (i.e. in case they move geographically), requires a collaborative effort across Europe.
3. Data sharing to make informed decisions and conclusions about the care of AYA is not possible due to a number of challenges – including risks to data privacy and protection and different ways of applying ethical principles to data collection, management and sharing over time and between countries.
4. The STRONG-AYA Consortium aims to build a sustainable pan-European ecosystem that addresses some of these challenges through a defined set of principles, rules for joining the ecosystem and making data available for privacy-preserving federated learning, for the benefit of AYA care across Europe.
5. This document outlines the governing principles of the pan-European ecosystem to be adhered to by current and new members, the process of becoming a member, and the rules for contributing to, benefiting from, and ensuring the sustainability of a growing federated learning infrastructure. It also lays out the limitations, facilitators, risks and mitigations for each element of our pan-European ecosystem, and the next methods and metrics required for further progress

10.5. Introduction

10.1. Project background

Adolescents and young adults (AYAs) with cancer form a unique group; they face age-specific issues and decreased quality of life. Cancer in AYAs aged 15-39 is rare, although 4-6 times more frequent than paediatric cancer (i.e. prepubescent period). However, this rarity does not reflect the significant personal and societal costs of cancer in this population, as reflected in the potential years of life lost or saved, the decreased productivity and quality of life and the life-long complications or disabilities¹.

Improving survival in AYA is more challenging than for children and older cancer survivors. This is partly due to the excess risk of second primary malignant neoplasms identified in this group compared to cohorts of younger and older patients². Moreover, AYAs face some distinct challenges compared to older and younger counterparts in the treatment of their primary or secondary malignancies - a unique spectrum of cancer types, different tumour biology, unique complex psychological needs, distinct late sequelae, including impaired fertility, and palliative care^{3,4}.

¹ Stoneham SJ. AYA survivorship: The next challenge. *Cancer* 2020; 126: 2116-2119.

² Keegan THM, Bleyer A, Rosenberg AS et al. Second Primary Malignant Neoplasms and Survival in Adolescent and Young Adult Cancer Survivors. *JAMA Oncol* 2017; 3: 1554-1557.

³ Bleyer A, Barr R, Hayes-Lattin B et al. The distinctive biology of cancer in adolescents and young adults. *Nat Rev Cancer* 2008; 8: 288-98.

⁴ Ferrari A, Stark D, Peccatori FA et al. Adolescents and young adults (AYA) with cancer: a position paper from the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOPE). *ESMO Open* 2021; 6: 100096.

These consequences imply that the clinical management, treatment, diagnosis, and psychosocial support need to be designed and developed for the specific needs of AYA. For example, AYAs diagnosed with breast and prostate carcinomas have worse survival than older patients because of the biological differences, highlighting the need to target screening methodologies, treatments, and policies to their needs. AYAs with cancer also face significant psychological challenges, including substance abuse, mental health issues, suicidal ideations, and increased emotional burden from cancer and cancer-related morbidity. Finally, tailoring cancer care to AYAs' needs is also made difficult by the low rate of participation by AYAs in clinical trials and cancer research⁵.

Despite the increasing awareness and a growing body of the scientific literature, European health systems have not fully recognised and addressed the unique issues faced by AYAs with cancer, and therefore these individuals often do not receive the right type of support. In part, this may have resulted from the traditional dichotomy between the integrated paediatric (“patient/family-centred”) care services versus dispersed (“disease-centred”) adult oncology services^{4,6,7}. As a result, up to half of AYAs with cancer report unmet informational and service needs, impacting both their direct (survival rates) and indirect (long-term effects and mental health) recovery and social integration⁸.

Furthermore, aligned with this barrier is the low rate of health care utilisation by AYAs, especially primary care, in part due to low awareness of AYA malignancy among primary carers and, depending on the nation, due to challenges to sustain health insurance coverage⁵. According to a survey conducted through the networks of the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOP Europe), 67% of practitioners do not have access to specialised centres for AYA with cancer, 67% had no access to a specialist cancer service for late effects management and 38% had no access to fertility specialists. Under-provision and inequality of AYA cancer care is common across Europe and especially in the Eastern and Southern-Eastern areas. Furthermore, the Working Group also reported an absence of outcome measures for monitoring and evaluating AYA cancer care programs⁹.

Among the recommended future steps, one of the most important contributions to AYA research would be to pool data (e.g. patient-reported outcomes, clinical and treatment data) across institutions and countries and create large cohorts for researchers to address the burden of cancer in AYA¹⁰. However, there are challenges due to a lack of data standardisation, data interoperability, unitary (prospective) collection of outcomes of relevance for AYAs with cancer, data privacy and security concerns, as well as regional differences in the application of ethical principles governing data collection and sharing.

The STRONG-AYA project aims to tackle the underrepresentation of AYA's experiences and outcomes when navigating the healthcare system and in clinical care by developing national infrastructures for outcome data management and clinical decision-making within a pan-European ecosystem and establishing communication feedback for AYAs with cancer and their healthcare systems. This will be key to improving healthcare services, research, outcomes and policies for AYAs and to ultimately improved cancer care for this patient group.

⁵ Hayashi RJ. Adolescent and young adult cancer survivorship: The new frontier for investigation. *Cancer* 2019; 125: 1976-1978.

⁶ Osborn M, Johnson R, Thompson K et al. Models of care for adolescent and young adult cancer programs. *Pediatr Blood Cancer* 2019; 66: e27991.

⁷ Fardell JE, Patterson P, Wakefield CE et al. A Narrative Review of Models of Care for Adolescents and Young Adults with Cancer: Barriers and Recommendations. *J Adolesc Young Adult Oncol* 2018; 7: 148-152.

⁸ Keegan TH, Lichtensztajn DY, Kato I et al. Unmet adolescent and young adult cancer survivors information and service needs: a population-based cancer registry study. *J Cancer Surviv* 2012; 6: 239-250.

⁹ Saloustros E, Stark D, Michailidou K et al. Report on ESMO/SIOPE European Landscape project key results: Mapping the status and needs in AYA cancer care. Late-breaking and deferred publication abstracts public health 2017; 28, 5: V643.

¹⁰ Smith AW, Seibel NL, Lewis DR et al. Next steps for adolescent and young adult oncology workshop: An update on progress and recommendations for the future. *Cancer* 2016; 122: 988-999.

Building on previous initiatives, a STRONG-AYA federated learning ecosystem has been set up for the implementation of value-based care, research, and policy for AYA with cancer. This is being achieved through: the **Development of a Core Outcomes Set (COS)** specifically for AYAs; **implementing the COS across several national European healthcare systems for retrospective and prospective data analyses**, and by **disseminating the COS analyses, their interpretation and implications to European stakeholders**. For more information on these objectives, please refer to D3.3. Technical Blueprint¹¹. Implementing these project objectives are five work packages (WPs) within the STRONG-AYA project:

- WP1: Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer and Data Collection (Lead: SOUTHAMPTON)
- WP2: Governance, Data Security and Ethics (Lead: EORTC)
- WP3: Infrastructure and Interoperability (Lead: UNIMAAS)
- WP4: Operation of STRONG-AYA ecosystems, Stakeholder and Patient involvement, Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication (Lead: E.C.O.)
- WP5: Scientific Coordination and Project Management (Lead: NKI).

This report defines the rules and actions governing the functioning of the pan-European ecosystem (WP4) with a view to ensuring sustainable and ongoing collaboration, preservation of privacy, and research robustness and ethics.

10.2. Definition of the pan-European ecosystem

As defined in D4.4¹², our pan-European ecosystems consist of:

- communities of people (healthcare providers, researchers, policy makers, lived experience co-researchers, etc.),
- of their securely held data, governed within a federated learning system for joint data preparation, quality assurance, analysis and interpretation, and
- relevant web-based tools and resources on which all stakeholders can co-operate, view appropriate information and outputs from the research that are relevant to them, interact with research findings and communities, and request additional relevant appropriate data analyses.

The STRONG-AYA pan-European ecosystem aims to enable AYA care and research to benefit from the collection and joint analysis of clinical and patient-reported data, and a wider collaboration among all stakeholders: patients, healthcare professionals, scientists, and policymakers. More widely, our consortium aims to leverage the network of interested organisations and experts, established under STRONG-AYA, for long-term strong promotion of the implementation of specialist AYA cancer services across Europe.

¹¹ [D3.3 TECHNICALBLUEPRINT STRONGAYA v2.pdf](#), page 9.

¹² [D4.4 OVERARCHING OPERATIONAL PLAN NATIONAL STRONG AYA V.1.pdf](#), pages 8-9.

Local STRONG-AYA ecosystems, and we plan soon national ecosystems are to be connected within an overarching pan-European ecosystem (see Figure 1) to enable the shared analysis of data, a repository for sharing reports, analytical tools and educational materials. It will also act as a prototype for future growth of other national STRONG-AYA ecosystems, each feeding into our pan-European system.

Figure 1: Structure of the national and pan-European ecosystem in the STRONG-AYA Consortium. National ecosystems (Italy, UK, Netherlands, France, and Poland) where datasets are generated and stored at local and national level, become integrated within the pan-European ecosystem through federated learning

Figure 2: The relation between the constituent parts of Strong-AYA

10.3. Implementation of Federated Learning

To generate robust, well-powered analyses, which can generate valuable insights for AYA’s clinical and psychosocial care, while maintaining data safety, privacy, and alignment to ethical principles, the Consortium is taking a federated learning (FL) approach.

Federated learning refers to a group of computational methodologies where statistical questions or problems¹³ can be answered cooperatively without exchanging identifiable human subject data between any of the cooperating institutions. The “Personal Health Train” (PHT)¹⁴ is a manifesto for implementing FL that describes the technological, governance, and procedural components needed to execute a fully working FL infrastructure. From a procedural point of view, PHT will not allow the exchange of identifiable individual patient-level data between institutions to generate epidemiological models or statistical summaries. Instead, focused algorithms are sent from the central server to each ‘data station’ for immediate analysis (or aggregation) to help answer a question or solve an intended research or statistical problem. Governance is essential in terms of compliance to local and international privacy laws, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹⁵, and the allocation of intellectual property rights between members of a consortium. The legal agreement templates required to facilitate PHT collaborations have been made openly accessible¹⁶.

Technologically, PHT requires three interdependent components to be set up. “Tracks” are the protected telecommunications links needed to transmit messages between a central model aggregation hub and the participating institutions. “Trains” are containerized software applications that carry a data query filter with some analysis code to be executed locally inside the institutional firewall. “Stations” are the institutional data repositories, which hold the actual patient data being used to fit a single global multi-institutional model.

FL comes with several advantages to how data access and analyses are performed, but also special considerations and operation rules defined further below. FL offers a way to process disparate, large, and complex datasets needed to accelerate findings in a specific health field and thereby increase the power, detail, and reach of insights. The ecosystem concept acknowledges and respects that data collection workflows and data management practices will be specific and already in use among the project partners, for numerous operational and research purposes. Datasets owned by each project partner will be used for the unitary common goal of answering pre-defined clinical and research questions (i.e. use cases). However, a few technical requirements do need to be met to ensure the effectiveness and usability of the FL procedure, including a specific suite of specialised software for making data FAIR, for performing federated computations, and providing a graphical user interface to direct the federated analyses. More details on how the software (Docker application and Vantage6) operates and other technical requirements are available in the Technical Blueprint (D3.3)¹¹.

FL ecosystems are especially necessary within the ever-evolving and complex landscape related to data policy and security whereby real world health data (such as patient-reported outcomes) is a ‘special category’ and is legally challenging to transfer across borders or even institutions. As with data available in other rare diseases, the development of insights for improved outcomes and services pertaining to the features and outcomes of AYA cancers benefits from a concerted approach. A FL approach allows us to address the challenges of reduced accuracy due to small sample sizes and provides the grounds for richer and more robust insights into the need of new treatments and necessary adaptations of current ones to the target population (AYAs aged 15 to 39) compared to only relying on data from a single database. FL is a solution to the need for accessing multiple data repositories in multi-national and multi-jurisdictional

¹³ Wang J, Charles Z, Xu Z, et al. A field guide to federated optimization. arXiv. 2021. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2107.06917>

¹⁴ The Personal Health Train Network | The Personal Health Train. Available from: <https://www.health-ri.nl/en/personal-health-train-federated-learning>

¹⁵ General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) – Official Legal Text. Available from: <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

¹¹ [D3.3 TECHNICALBLUEPRINT STRONGAYA v2.pdf](#), page 9.

¹⁶Medical Data Works [Internet]. [cited 2024 Feb 10]. Available from: <https://www.medicaldataworks.nl/governance>

contexts in a secure and fast manner. However, to reach these benefits at minimal risk, the design and implementation of FL systems requires careful consideration of the content and security of access to sensitive health data, clarity in the design of the data system, guidelines regarding who and how they can be accessed, with particular attention to governance structures internationally and within individual countries.

We further define the governance model of the STRONG-AYA pan-European ecosystem, consistent with principles and processes previously outlined by the World Economic Forum¹⁷, with a particular view to the individuals actively involved or who may be involved later down the line. We detail how new actors' incentives which should align with that of the existing Consortium (i.e. improving patient outcomes and health care delivery) to ensure robust security and dynamically improving policy and to safeguard against modern data-access challenges (bad or unclear motives, data breaches or any other types of preventable risks).

11. Governance model

Through the STRONG-AYA Consortium, federating data provides an opportunity to gain insights in high volumes of heterogeneous data for patient benefit. It also enables members to align and resolve differences in successfully navigating distinct local, national, and supranational data policy laws, security and privacy protocols, and data interoperability. The governance model developed and enacted within STRONG-AYA defines how the pan-European ecosystem will operate, including:

1. **Its foundational principles:** which should guide future decision-making and thresholds for defining criteria and rules.
2. **The structure of the Consortium:** with member responsibilities and criteria for joining and maintaining an active presence in the ecosystem while it is expected to grow and change.
3. **Aligning incentives/motives and actions** to ensure it achieves the group's shared goals.
4. **Clear standards acting as the rules for day-to-day operations and dispute resolution.**
5. **Federated use of data** and minimum ground rules for access, formatting and typology standardisation.
6. **Sustainability of the project**, while ethical standards (incl. rules for informing, consenting and sharing insights with patients) are dynamic and evolve.
7. **Technical standards** for the data security, integrity, privacy and rules of access which must always keep up to pace with emerging threats and any new regulations.
8. **Intellectual property sharing.**
9. **Sharing of benefits** arising from the use of the federated data ecosystem between members.

Our governance model is led from within our ecosystem (self-governed) and is open and inclusive across its countries of operation. Specifically, the STRONG-AYA Consortium adheres to a set of principles (detailed below) which encourage other similar experts to join the same goals with shared commitment in the production of scientific insights, ensuring transparency in data, inclusiveness, collaboration, and sustainability.

¹⁷ World Economic Forum. Sharing Sensitive Health Data in a Federated Data Consortium Model. An Eight-Step Guide. 2020. Accessed Feb 2024. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/sharing-sensitive-health-data-in-a-federated-data-consortium-model-an-eight-step-guide/>

11.1. Structure of the Consortium

11.1.1. Existing Consortium partners

STRONG-AYA brings together an international multi-disciplinary Consortium across seven European countries, led by the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI). The Consortium is currently composed of academic research organisations, clinical partners, stakeholder and patient organisations, and a consulting company, as described in the General Consortium Agreement. However, we expect other stakeholders, whose ethical principles align to those of STRONG-AYA, to be interested in joining this initiative.

11.1.2. Committee for Coordination

The main organisations which make up the structure of the pan-European ecosystem have set up the Committee for Coordination (CfC) with specific roles as the ecosystem grows and changes within the dynamic context of value-based health care and research. Namely, it:

1. Defines the responsibilities of members, including our Patient Advisory Board
2. Defines and implements criteria for newly joining members
3. Encourages an active presence and adherence to founding principles
4. Encourages communication among national ecosystems
5. Ensures consistency, standardisation and harmonisation of data
6. Promotes scalability to and within countries
7. Contributes to and guarantees the sustainability of the network of ecosystems once the project is finished.

The CfC is embedded within the European ecosystem, is composed of the leaders of the local/national ecosystems (PIs at founding STRONG-AYA member-institutions in the first instance), patient advocate(s), and is informed by the reports and feedback of other working packages and the functioning of local ecosystems. It is responsible for defining the minimum requirements set for additional countries and institutions to adhere to as they become part of the Consortium. Meetings and periodical communication will be established to favour regular and constructive communication among the members of the CfC and to ensure its sustainability beyond the lifetime of the funding for this project.

11.2. Founding principles

There is an expectation that new members as well as their internal systems will follow and abide by the same principles as the original Consortium members. The CfC has a critical role in ensuring these principles – some general to federated ecosystems, and some specific to STRONG-AYA, are adhered to internally and that newly joining members have ethical principles aligned to that of the existing Consortium.

11.2.1. Value-based healthcare

STRONG-AYA seeks to use data-driven insights as a starting level of evidence to drive developments in research, care, and policy.

AYA cancer is considered 'rare' in oncology with an incidence rate of less than 6 per 100,000 persons per year. This means that clinical experience is diluted, AYA cancer is more likely to be diagnosed at advanced stage, and conducting clinical trials is more challenging. For the studies that do exist, numbers of subjects are unavoidably small, making statistically significant findings difficult and therefore it is unclear what are the potentially actionable insights to improve healthcare. By broadening the research using novel privacy-safe approaches towards data analytics, STRONG-AYA will bring novel insights into AYA healthcare, encourage

ethical re-use of scarce AYA research data, provide real-world evidence to all important AYA oncology decision-makers, and thus, increase the benefit for patients by making care more efficient.

11.2.2. FAIR data

Data contributed to the ecosystem needs to be:

- **Findable** – easy to find by both humans and computers, through the use of unique and persistent identifiers, defined by rich, clear, and explicit metadata, within a researchable location.
- **Accessible** – data can be identified and retrieved via standardised communication protocols, by using authentication and authorisation procedures; metadata should still be accessible even if data is no longer available.
- **Interoperable** – the data can be integrated with other data and interoperate with other applications for analysis, storage, processing; (meta)data uses a shared, formal, accessible language and is defined using FAIR principles.
- **Reusable** – both metadata and data have to be structured and well described in a replicable manner so that they can be used in various settings.

STRONG-AYA follows the FAIR data management principles. This means that data remains findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable while it stays fully private under the direct control of the individual institutions. The FAIR principles will accordingly be applied at partner, national and pan-European levels for data, and subsequent digital artefacts (e.g., software, publications, reports) generated from the project work.

11.2.3. Open science

STRONG-AYA abides by the principle that the research pursued, insights generated using the data (including publications, the data itself, software etc.) and its disseminations are accessible to all stakeholders and public, the methods are transparent and accessible, and the knowledge is developed, shared and can be used across the ecosystem. UNIMAAS and IKNL commit to all computer code being openly accessible and constantly reviewable/critiqued. All UNIMAAS publications related to STRONG-AYA will be open access and covered by the relevant EU funding. Any dissemination activities are openly available to members of the wider public as well as specialists, via a register maintained by the STRONG-AYA Project Coordinator.

While most insights and products will be accessible to all within the STRONG-AYA ecosystem, as well as the methods to produce these, the level to which the datasets can be accessed and what is queried will depend on the type of stakeholder requesting access and their motives. Therefore, while all methods and disseminations will be open access, access to patient data ('data stations') will not, adhering to data protection and patient privacy principles (see below).

11.2.4. Transparency

The basis for collecting new (prospective) data, requesting access to specific data (i.e. submitting use cases), as well as the methods used to address questions need to be transparent, as detailed in the Code of Conduct (D2.2.)¹⁸. Transparency also needs to govern how existing (historical/retrospective) datasets have been collected and structured. This helps ensure all Consortium members understand the data, research questions and subsequent computations, and can readily evaluate if and when they can achieve their goals via federated analytics. Sharing plans related to novel dataset structures and characteristics can safeguard

¹⁸ [D2.2 ETHICALGUIDELINES CODEOFCONDUCT STRONGAYA v1.pdf](#), page 10

against a single Consortium member being the majority data owner which would create structural inequity and power conflicts at the decision making level.

For the purpose of equity in data provision and data queries and hence to reduce misalignment resulting from power democracy, the STRONG-AYA pan-European ecosystem will ensure:

- **Data stewardship and control will be jointly held by Principal investigators (PIs) and their teams of investigators.** That is because focusing power only on the PI would remove the institutional investigators from the power structure and the data governance loop. Through joint power over data we ensure the context and subtlety related to data is maintained, and if data needs to be enriched, enhanced or requires additional management, this can be done in partnership within the local ecosystems, rather than it being the responsibility of a single person.
- **The actions herein are not a new topology of ‘data control exercise’ by a single partner.** That is, it is important that all partners are equal in terms of suggesting a use case (as long as it is congruent with the foundational data usage principles and incentives of the consortium) and all partners must have the same “power” in terms of being able to run an analysis and test their hypotheses. The consortium will ensure no one partner makes all the rules and no partner becomes a mere data-feeding station. “Joint controllership” according to GDPR – in terms of the data contributions by each partner and the analyses being run on each others datasets - becomes a central tenet of the legal basis for data usage and it is specified as part of the data protection agreement signed by consortium members.
- **The federation must still be able to function (albeit in such cases on a reduced data sample) if one partner conscientiously opts out of a particular analysis or use case.** The actions and operations within the ecosystem are not ‘all-in or all-out’. For instance, it may be that a healthcare provider wants to be part of sarcoma studies but wants to opt out of breast cancer studies. From the STRONG-AYA consortium perspective, this complies with the principle of enshrined autonomy of each investigator in the consortium. This also respects local processes and obligations and regulations; for example sociodemographic data collection and analysis is permitted in the UK, but is illegal in France. The opt-out of French centres from such analyses is thus imperative and so maintaining a more flexible approach is an inclusive, rather than exclusive, structure.

In the case of prospective (novel) data collection (such as PROs based on the COS), each local partner needs to ensure that transparency is present in communication with participants. This means that all participants have provided and documented informed consent, which contains the relevant information about data processing and data protection aligned to article 13 of the GDPR, including any local institutional guidelines and best practices.

In the case of retrospective (historical) data available and provided by partners, article 4 of GDPR applies, thereby the data collected by a partner must meet all three grounds allowing the processing of such data. Namely, the data can be processed if a) the participant offered freely given, specific, and informed consent (Article 6 (1) (a)); b) processing is a legitimate interest exception such as there is a legitimate interest of controllers AND the legitimate interest cannot reasonably be achieved by using alternative means AND the interests and fundamental rights and freedom of the participant do not take precedence over the legitimate interests of the controller(s); c) the data is anonymised and therefore falls outside GDPR. As an example, a legitimate interest exception would be that of testing hypotheses for the purpose of public health.

Finally, honoring this principle means that participants should find it easy to understand how specific information about their health is used or accessed. Participants should easily and reliably have control and be able to access their health data and they should be able to exercise these rights. Exactly what type of data

patients versus healthcare professionals will be able to see is decided by the CfC in collaboration with the entire consortium and the Patient Advisory Board to avoid undue distress or harmful decision making.

11.2.5. Standardisation of data

One of the limitations identified in summarising and making valuable conclusions for clinical decisions in AYA's clinical care internationally is the lack of data standardisation. This relates to the changing landscape of healthcare professional- and patient-reported outcomes that are considered relevant for the treatment, care, and research in AYA cancers. As AYAs are an under-researched demographic and straddle the traditional divisions between paediatric and adult oncology, the type of care an AYA experiences varies significantly between paediatric and adult oncological institutions, between regions, and between countries.

Within the STRONG-AYA ecosystem we acknowledge that there will be some misalignment of data fields collected within an institution across time, and also between institutions at any given time. Datasets collected in the past will not have been structured the same way as newer ones as organisations learned and developed. As a result, across the Consortium, there will be a high heterogeneity in the collection of some domains, particularly those reliant on PROs, and only some will have been recorded systematically. As PROs will, alongside clinical data, drive insights related to tailored treatment and care, STRONG-AYA is committed to standardising the type and method of PRO data collected across the Consortium for the purposes of interoperability and sustainability. Within STRONG-AYA we will strive for a standardisation of an optimum minimal level of data.

To ensure the data ecosystem is used as effectively and efficiently for analyses and insights, the Consortium relies on the work in WP1 related to the COS, WP2 in relation to data minimisation, WP3 in relation to joint controllership agreements related to data and visualisation methods, and importantly local ethical reviews for the appropriate collection and use of local data. Going forward, by establishing a COS for AYA care and using data-driven insights gathered via our pan-European ecosystem, STRONG-AYA will share insights with policy-makers to address and reduce inequalities across the entire disease pathway of different cancers in AYAs in different regions in Europe, towards our aim of establishing a European-wide standard of care. STRONG-AYA will enable AYA healthcare quality outcomes monitoring by tracking access, such as by AYA nurse specialists, fertility consultants, and social workers for discussion about work and establish benchmarking between the different countries on key performance indicators.

11.2.6. Inclusion, focused upon patient benefit

STRONG-AYA tools and activities are patient-centred and based on the European Ethical Principles for Digital Health, following the principle of 'nothing about me without me'. These ethical principles, centred on the interests and values of patients, are the foundation the Consortium builds upon, are reiterated and reflected in the development of the FL ecosystem, and built through stakeholder engagement and reflections from the Patient Advisory Board. Importantly, any tools and actions within STRONG-AYA are meant to complement and optimise face-to-face healthcare, patients are informed both of the benefits and limits of tools developed by the Consortium, and they can customise their interactions with these tools.

Furthermore, through work currently underway in WP4 by engaging patients in the development of the research and tools, STRONG-AYA aims to ensure patient-facing tools and resulting conclusions are accessible. Namely, STRONG-AYA will ensure patients:

- Are able to easily and reliably access/retrieve their own STRONG-AYA health data (through their own hospital systems)
- See their own health data in the context of other AYA similar to them

- Easily access information on how their health data has been accessed or used and for what purpose, such that they should be able to easily enhance, grant or remove access to their health data depending upon their perspective on each 'case of use' of their data, and exercise this right freely
- Any tools developed by STRONG-AYA need to be inclusive and accessible to all (including by people with disabilities or low levels of digital literacy). They should be intuitive and easy to use, patients should have access to training to help them understand digital health tools, which in turn should be implemented in care routines that also include human communication.
- Patient representation on the CfC will ensure that a patient voice is embedded in the ecosystem's governing structure

Clinical trials and medical research, historically, have been driven by the questions and concerns clinicians and researchers wished to investigate. However, it is patients who are directly impacted by the outcomes of research. Their questions and concerns should be placed on equal footing with clinical research areas of interest. By involving patients in the process of co-creation, STRONG-AYA will create a platform that serves patients and empowers them by further increasing their health literacy.

Following upon the above, STRONG-AYA will equip AYAs with cancer with the data to better optimise their healthcare, and support shared and personalised decision-making between AYA and health care providers. This also extends to the control of, access to, and use of AYA's data in the context of research and healthcare. Importantly, by involving patient groups in the conversations around the actions and operations within the ecosystem and the co-creation of the patient platform and methods of data visualisation, the Consortium is committed to 'meaningful' patient participation leading to actionable patient-centred and patient-informed insights. The effort of co-creation is expected to result both via the local/national-level governance and ethical systems which are dedicated to incorporating patients' views, but also through the guiding principles of the consortium.

11.2.7. Privacy, and confidentiality-preserving

By adopting a FL and federated analysis approach, the privacy and confidentiality of the participant is protected. Details of how this is performed can be found in D3.3 Technical Blueprint¹¹. Here we simply offer a general overview of how STRONG-AYA will meet this foundational principle. Specifically, we will adhere to both GDPR at an international level and local data protection regulations in what concerns the levels of data anonymization or pseudonymisation for federated learning.

Within STRONG-AYA we make a distinction between:

1. federated analyses that do not exchange ANY individual patient information, ONLY group-level statistical summaries (e.g. averages, confidence intervals, regression coefficients) and
2. analyses that during the computation process will unavoidably exchange outcome labels of individuals (e.g. alive/deceased), but these would need additional data in order to identify the individual.

The first point encompasses one of the technological cornerstones of the project - **federated analytics**. Statistical analyses and descriptive statistical visualisations on groups of participants will be performed without transmitting any individual patient-level data outside of the data owning institution. The second point relates to STRONG-AYA supporting **federated learning** – a method of developing epidemiological statistical models on a group of participants, without transmitting identifiable patient-level data between institutions. Some epidemiological models will require the exchange of the frequencies of certain outcomes to answer research questions – such as 'alive (or deceased)', 'diagnosis positive (or negative) or a time interval (such as '90 days since a certain event'). In some circumstances, such an outcome may be

characteristic to only 1 participant. However, without individual additional data the individual cannot be re-identified, but such specific individual data will not be accessible via the ecosystem and federated learning infrastructure. Therefore, privacy protection in federated learning and analytics is based on the unfeasibility of reverse-engineering a particular participants' identity on the basis of summaries, statistical models or other such combined data analyses results based on groups of participants (which are also typically presented in reports and publications)¹¹.

Finally, the development of the COS is based on the idea of data minimization – structured data for the COS is extracted by investigators within each institution and placed in their respective STRONG-AYA secure environment controlled by their own institution and governed by their own data protection regulations. All data placed in these areas will be checked to ensure it is pseudonymised or anonymised (as necessary) consistent with the STRONG-AYA Data Protection Agreement to avoid the re-identification of individuals and in accordance both with GDPR and local regulations. For instance, identifiable information which is not necessary for analyses such as birth dates and postcodes is not allowed. No dates will be stored in the STRONG-AYA repository, only time ranges. Similarly, to avoid re-identification, no analyses will be run if the count of participants at the intersection of the criteria query falls below 10.

11.2.8. Scalability and sustainability

As outlined in the Business architecture (D2.1¹⁹), the STRONG-AYA Consortium is committed to the principle of **scalability** of its resulting activities, tools, and pan-European ecosystem – namely, translatable to other contexts - and their **sustainability** – namely, to last beyond the lifetime of the research project. This will be done through the operations of the ecosystem outlined here, through the delivery of the COS, through federated learning mechanisms, the delivery of usable and inclusive tools, and adaptability to changing ethics and governance landscapes.

The development the COS for AYAs with cancer enables STRONG-AYA to offer new opportunities for the collection of homogeneous prospective data, which will support new research and healthcare innovation. The agile and adaptable approach of FL allows flexibility in incorporating existing systems and practices in larger ecosystems, allowing for the accommodation of new local contexts and ecosystems. Tools which will enable and motivate stakeholders to join and work together are the websites, specific ways of set-up of local databases, portals for stakeholders to enter and access desired information, and finally the access to the expertise required to operate ecosystems at local and European levels. Finally, STRONG-AYA will remain responsive to emerging and unanticipated ethical issues by adhering to iteratively developed ethical guidance throughout the duration of the project, including patient-centered and patient-informed ethical guidance. The sustainability of these aspects will be ensured via the CfC.

Continuous ethical monitoring is important because not all ethical issues can be foreseen – some concerns and implications of building a new research data infrastructure and configuring new alliances will have unanticipated consequences. By using an iterative ethical guidance method, STRONG-AYA aims to respond to relevant ethical and governance issues with a reflexive approach, attending to concerns as they arise from the developing research infrastructure and collaborative research actions. To do so, STRONG-AYA draws on expertise within the Consortium to organize suitable platforms and formats of patient

¹¹[D3.3 TECHNICALBLUEPRINT STRONGAYA v2.pdf](#)

¹⁹[D2.1 ECOSYSTEM BUSINESS ARCHITECTURE STRONGAYA 2023 FINAL1.pdf](#)

consultation that result in meaningful patient participation and leads to actionable patient-centered and patient-informed insights²⁰.

Through these, STRONG-AYA aims to generate a strong culture of successful and sustainable means of working together as well as the integration between clinical epidemiological and data science processes with the views of stakeholders. There is an expectation that the ecosystem will speed up analyses on cancer in AYA which should lead to faster decision-making in terms of treatment and care.

11.3. Aligned incentives and motives, across Consortium members

All Consortium members are expected to be transparent in communicating their incentives and motives for joining a FL Consortium. This will help the functioning of the pan-European ecosystem by offering a general view of the expectations and responsibilities of different users at local, national, and ultimately pan-European levels.

The STRONG-AYA Consortium is committed to satisfying the goals of each partner, flexibly, hence transparency and specificity in incentives is needed for a purposeful collaboration. The alignment of incentives and motives relies on a keen understanding of each institution's capacity to achieve its goals through the joining of a FL ecosystem. This translates into having the means and mature enough processes for data collection and storage, or processes which can be optimised with some support - for instance ensuring alignment with the technical requirements outlined in the Technical Blueprint (D3.3)¹¹. This also pertains to the description of goals, objectives and key performance indicators leading to these (see D5.2)²¹. This will mean an alignment (with support from the Consortium expertise and experience) on capacity for clinical leadership, administrative power, scientific, technical, and ethical governance knowledge.

The ongoing incentives and motives for the existence of the STRONG-AYA Consortium and pan-European ecosystem are reflected in the principles outlined above. In short, they can be summarised as (for details, see D2.2 Code of Conduct¹⁸):

1. Improvement in the provision of healthcare services:

- The development of value-based clinical practice, that becomes responsive to new knowledge in real time
- Improving and accelerating the implementation of real-world insights into clinical practice.

2. Performing ethical research on large datasets:

- Encouraging international collaboration for research and clinical expertise
- Improving and expanding on the applications of available data in research
- Understanding and leveraging institutional capacity.

3. Improving the quality of patient outcomes:

- Defining and identifying patient needs – for research and clinical purposes
- Improving the reach of research and understanding of patient outcomes for patients from diverse backgrounds
- Improving patient outcomes through the use of real world data.

It is expected that different members will have differing priorities among these incentives for wanting to participate in the Consortium and this is acceptable. Furthermore, it is acknowledged that institutional incentives and motivations to join a Consortium can go beyond patient benefit in terms of the queries they

¹¹[D3.3 TECHNICALBLUEPRINT STRONGAYA v2.pdf](#)

¹⁸[D2.2 ETHICALGUIDELINES CODEOFCONDUCT STRONGAYA v1.pdf](#)

²⁰[D4.6 OPERATIONALPLANSNATIONALECOSYSTEMS STRONGAYA v.1.pdf](#)

²¹[D5.2 KPISandSUCCESSMETRICS STRONGAYA v.1.pdf](#)

may want to run. These can range from discovery (i.e. increasing volume of data to help manage rare diseases), improving and expanding on implementations of past initiatives (i.e. sharing workload on diverse datasets), or encouraging sustainable international collaboration (i.e. tangible outcomes can foster collaborative practices).

Whichever the motives of a potential new member, the main characteristic needs to be clinical actionability related to decisions on what queries can be run on the federated data. This also applies to how data is collected and monitored, what analyses can be pursued and which analyses can be shared or not with patients or healthcare providers. Hence, the purpose of data being collected, contributed to the data ecosystem and analysed will have a clearly defined clinical purpose for patient benefit, in line with the definition of ‘bona fide’ research as outlined in the Code of Conduct (D2.2) and regulated by local ethics boards. This will be a requirement for all professional stakeholders (i.e. new members of the Consortium) including healthcare, academic institutions, charities, policy makers, industry partners, etc.

The incentives guide the type of outcomes which are acceptable to our ecosystem, which outcomes are monitored, and therefore the design of use cases and data queries, how the local ecosystems are organised and the organisational capacity allocated or due to be developed for an active membership in the ecosystem. The CfC and existing Consortium members will promote the alignment of the different national ecosystems with these incentives and overall mission of the project for the promotion of scalability and sustainability.

11.4. Managing national and institutional differences

Within the definition of the governance model with its structure, principles and alignment of incentives and motives, the Consortium acknowledges the differences between institutions and countries in their capacity, capabilities, and limitations in what data can or cannot be used for federated learning or analyses. There is an expectation that not all countries and institutions will be able to fully meet all requirements (technical, administrative etc) and there will be gaps in policies. The ethos of a collaborative pan-European ecosystem is that these gaps can be bridged as part of the working practices. A task within the ecosystem needs to be the transparent communication and discussion of these potential differences and gaps to allow room for their troubleshooting and secondary plans to achieve explicit goals.

Before joining the Consortium, there is an expectation of local discussions with leadership, technical and legal teams akin to those pursued in D4.4. and D4.6 to identify local capacity. Local evaluation of data availability and metadata structuring, to identify strengths and opportunities for development at each national ecosystem level may be necessary. These interviews can be had with a third, impartial organisation but the resulting insights need to be shared with the CfC as part of the new member application process. Internal interviews and audits for insights into potential knowledge gaps should prompt local discussions (as exemplified by D4.4 and D4.6) and should incorporate at minimum the following categories:

A. Provision and availability of retrospective data: Is data available and can it be analysed?

**The questions below apply to retrospective data. Approvals in line with GDPR and local legal/ethical guidelines are expected to be arranged by consortium members.*

- What data is currently available, from previous studies or clinical practice?
- Did patients consent to their data being processed for public health research?
- Can the existing data be FAIR-ified?
- What is the local complaints procedure (i.e. immediacy of action, timeframes for reply etc)?

B. Data collection and consent norms for prospective data: How is data collected?

**The questions below apply to prospective studies. Appropriate Ethics Board approvals in line with GDPR and local legal and ethical guidelines will be expected to be in place in each location.*

- Do patients know why the data is being collected?
- Do patients agree to share the data?
- Do patients know why the data is being shared?
- Do patients understand how it is being shared?
- What is the local institutional process of communicating results back to patients (if necessary)?
- Does data collection follow pre-existing regulations and rules?
- What is the local complaints procedure (i.e. immediacy of action, timeframes for reply etc)?

C. Operational norms and standards: How does each institution operationalise the Consortium internally?

**Please read the current General Consortium Agreement for an example of how these questions can be answered by an applying member.*

- From whom will you accept a data query?
- For what purpose will you use (or allow use) of the data?
- What results will you allow to be returned?
- Who adjudicates disputes or ambiguous situations locally, in regards to data collection and analyses (either from participants or researchers)?
- What is the threshold to entry for a new member of the federations?

D. Technical standards: What are the technical standards (i.e. How are the datasets managed to guarantee data security, data integrity, and patient privacy)?

**Please read the current D3.3. Technical Blueprint and FAIR principle above, for an example of how these questions can be answered by an applying member. Within STRONG-AYA these are managed within WP3 with suitable software with clear sustainability plans available from IKNL.*

- How do you ensure security of queries within the transfer process?
- How is patient privacy protected?
- Do you make your build standards transparent?
- What is the change management process?
- What level of interoperability needs to be reached (in terms of software, APIs, and datasets)?
- What are your mechanisms for ensuring data integrity?
- How is data standardisation currently achieved?

E. Legal and ethical governance standards: What are the legal bases for consenting, collecting, and using patient data in research in each country and institution?

- Does a joining institution have consent and research process protocols and practices in place?
- Do these allow (and to what extent) for insight sharing as part of a federated learning ecosystem?

As an example, we expect at minimum to identify the following list of potential (not exhaustive) differences and gaps, which can then be leveraged and managed within the Consortium:

1. Availability of retrospective (historical) clinical and PROs data within centres
2. Ethical and governance rules towards the re-use of previously collected data for additional analyses or insights

3. Limitations in patient information and consent procedures at national levels for retrospective and prospective studies
4. National restrictions in collecting specific prospective data (e.g. in France collection of data pertaining to ethnicity is not permitted)
5. Ethical limitations in conducting particular analyses (i.e. cancer incidence by ethnicity)
6. Gaps in technical or administrative expertise in handling large data repositories
7. Potential differences or gaps in implementing software solutions, APIs, and managing data system upgrades or improvements in technical components
8. Time limitations in the storage and use of existing or new data.

12. Operations of the federated learning pan-European ecosystem

12.1. Summary

As described in section 5.2 and particularly in Figure 1, our pan-European ecosystem relies on the appropriate functioning of its parts – each local, and over time national, ecosystem with its own operational environment (described in detail in D4.4 and D4.6). Several interviews and focus groups with representatives of each national ecosystem evaluated the local and national ‘Preparedness’ of the human resources, technological, and data management and security infrastructures.

The Operational plan below acknowledges that our pan-European ecosystem can only evolve as fast as its parts (see Figure 1); we incorporate knowledge gathered through individual national interviews related to the healthcare and technological system readiness for a cross-country (and later cross-European) development of an ecosystem. While this may not be possible at a national level in each locale as yet, in certain parts of Europe our initiative has opened the doors to the development of the appropriate infrastructure to enable this beyond a local level in each nation. Our initiative highlighted the current threats and opportunities towards the goal of creating national ecosystems that can then be integrated with an international ecosystem. The status of ecosystem preparedness in each locale to develop towards a national and then European ecosystem is described in D4.4 and D4.6. D4.4 offers a detailed plan of the actions and issues all institutions within the STRONG-AYA consortium need to fulfill to operate their local ecosystems and build national AYA cancer ecosystems, including descriptions of people/human resources, priorities of actions, and pragmatics of implementing the federated ecosystem. D4.6 set out of number of individual actions from each partner that need to be met to operate their own local and national, and therefore underpin our pan-European ecosystem. These actions formed the individual roadmaps for each centre whose data will contribute to the European federated data. The update on national system preparedness is available in D4.9, which includes an update on system preparedness one year later following the initial evaluations described in D4.4.

Here we summarize the actions still needed across nations to reach the ambitious goal of a pan-European eco-system with multiple stakeholders at various levels of preparedness. Our plan below outlines the development and integration of national ecosystems into a pan-European data-sharing and research-driven ecosystem for AYAs with cancer. It includes critical actions around human resources, technology, data management, and security, and aligns with the overarching principles of data federation, ethical compliance, and stakeholder collaboration, ensuring sustainable growth across national and European frameworks.

12.2. Operational objectives

- Establish a collaborative data ecosystem for AYAs with cancer, including in each participating location and across nations.
- Ensure secure, scalable data management and monitoring across local and national ecosystems.
- Drive patient-centered care and outcome-based analysis through the integration of COS and clinical data associated with the COS at local and national levels.
- Promote sustainable collaboration across all participating nations.

12.3. Scope of Work

- Support the development of individual local and national ecosystems, each tailored to local contexts, regulations, and healthcare needs.
- Implement a federated data infrastructure that allows secure sharing across local, national, and international ecosystems.
- Establish governance, data security, and ethical frameworks consistent with national and EU standards.
- Define local actions, milestones, and resources needed for a functional ecosystem.

12.4. Work Structure:

1. Ecosystem Setup

- Define national ecosystem leaders and teams.
- Establish local infrastructure for data collection and storage (e.g., Secure Research Environments).

2. Technology and Data Integration

- Implement federated data systems for secure cross-border data access.
- Install portals for data submission and monitoring in each ecosystem.

3. Governance and Compliance

- Align local ecosystems with GDPR and relevant ethical frameworks.
- Obtain legal approvals and consent forms for data sharing.

4. Stakeholder Involvement

- Engage patients, healthcare providers, and local governments.
- Implement cultural and language adaptations in patient portals.

5. Continuous Monitoring and Control

- Regular security audits.
- Ongoing risk management to address potential cyber-attacks and resource constraints.

12.5. National Ecosystems

The status of this work as of 30/09/2024 is detailed in D4.4 and 4.6, following detailed interviews with ecosystem leaders in each location and nation.

Stakeholder engagement in collaborative communities is strong in each nation, except for national data policy-makers.

Data access, currently based upon data altruism and mutual trust, is delayed, due to some academic delays (in defining the Core Outcome dataset to be collected), information technology system limitations and upgrades, and research culture barriers for AYA research, each in some locations.

Data management expertise and capacity is in place or imminent in each partner centre, to ensure metadata and data quality.

Recent research grant awards are facilitating widening our data access in France. Other research grant applications can contribute to the breadth of our pan-European ecosystem, if funded. There are successes and ongoing progress plans in each nation

- **The Netherlands:** Secure data storage is in place in local hospitals covering the whole nation. Data transfer agreements and protocols for existing data from existing studies (e.g. COMPRAYA) are ongoing.
- **UK:** Aspirations to obtain existing national data from NCRAS have been slowed by reduced governmental funding. Clinical leaders for AYA cancer in NCRAS are addressing this to achieve a specific limited national dataset, through key stakeholders (TYAC, Christie NHS Trust).
- **France:** New research grant aware will enable wider data access. Regulatory approval for COS data collection is delayed by the finalization of the COS.
- **Italy:** Local research dataset in place, from previous projects. A secure infrastructure for data is in development.
- **Poland:** Stakeholders in Warsaw are building a local research environment.

12.6. Technology and Data Management

- **Federated Data Infrastructure:** Each nation retains local control over its data, contributing aggregate data summaries for cross-European analysis.
- **Data Governance:** Ensure that the data collection and transfer adhere to the **FAIR principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).
- **Tools:** Web-based applications and portals will allow real-time and on-demand analysis of the collected data. These tools will integrate patient and provider feedback loops to enhance decision-making.

12.7. Human Resources Management

- Each center is recruiting and training local data managers and support staff to ensure compliance with data collection and analysis protocols.
- Organize workshops to train local healthcare providers on data collection and interpretation for AYAs.

12.8. Data collection (COS and clinical information) Monitoring and Uptake

- Implement training for both clinicians and patients to increase the usage of COS.
- Regular evaluations of COS integration into routine clinical practices in countries running the implementation study.

12.9. Data Security and Risk Management

- **Cybersecurity:** Regular software audits (e.g., vantage6 software) to ensure ecosystem-wide security.
- **Risk Mitigation:** Prepare backup plans for delayed regulatory approvals, insufficient funding, or personnel shortages.

12.10. Key Milestones, ahead of a fully functioning Strong-AYA pan-European ecosystem

- Initial setup of local and/or national ecosystems (2025).
- Secure data transfer and interoperability testing across all participating nations (2025).
- Successful implementation of COS across planned healthcare centers (2024-5).
- Final audits and certification of data security protocols (2024-5).
- Full integration of COS in routine practice and training for professionals to use it (2025-6).

12.11. Budget and Resource Allocation

- Each country is allocating resources for infrastructure, staff, and training.
- Secure long-term funding for the national and pan-European ecosystem, especially for data security infrastructure.

12.12. Timeline

Currently we are operating local ecosystems in most countries, with some limited national infrastructures in UK and France. The only true national care ecosystem currently functions in the Netherlands, and a national integrated health ecosystem is emerging, with all other local and national systems following suit. The plan going forward is:

- Setup, align and pilot national ecosystems in UK and France
- Develop agreement for national ecosystems in Italy and Poland.
- Integration of existing local and national ecosystems into a pan-European ecosystem of clinical centres, as a proof-of-concept, with continuous monitoring.

This operational plan reflects a collaborative approach, ensuring both local autonomy and unified objectives across nations to develop a robust, secure, and scalable ecosystem for adolescent and young adult cancer care. Our bespoke approach integrates the specific operational requirements highlighted in D4.4 and D4.6, while maintaining alignment with the broader goals and structure of this overarching pan-European operational plan.

13. Standards and Rules for the federated learning ecosystem

This next section focuses upon the day-to-day operations of the ecosystem, including standards and rules to be followed by ongoing and new partners for accessing the ecosystem, as well as pathways to dispute resolution.

13.1. Rules for ongoing and new partners

New partners are encouraged to join the STRONG-AYA Consortium and pan-European ecosystem through an application process, which will be reviewed by the Consortium leaders using frameworks developed by the CfC. We expect applications to be made, at minimum, from any of the types of stakeholders defined as:

- Researchers (academic, public health professionals, clinical researchers, market research organisations, etc.)
- Innovators (healthcare industry, e.g. pharmaceutical, medical devices)
- Regulatory authorities and payers (e.g. EMA, health insurers, healthcare regulatory bodies, health technology assessment agencies)
- Policy-makers working on AYA cancer research and care policies (e.g. specific departments in European Commission, national cancer and health authorities)
- Hospital managers and hospital federations
- Stakeholder organisations involved in AYA advocacy (e.g. patient organisations and support groups, field-specific charities/fundraising organisations) as well as individual patients.

The good practice rules to be followed by all ongoing and joining members, are detailed on page 14 of the D2.2. Code of conduct ([D2.2. ETHICALGUIDELINES_CODEOFCONDUCT_STRONGAYA_v1.pdf](#)).

13.2. Application requirements

As a Consortium we distinguish between patient-users for own/personal benefit, versus professional users on behalf of organisations who will use the system for education and research purposes. The following checklist refers to professional entities wishing to become members.

Potential new professional members wishing to join the Consortium and ecosystem will first need to confirm they have reviewed the relevant documents produced by the STRONG-AYA Consortium, on which this current document relies upon. These documents outline the minimum criteria partners should aim to meet and put in place – newly joining partners should confirm they are aware of these and are taking actions to meeting them. This includes at minimum: the Consortium General Grant Agreement, the Technical Blueprint, the Data Management Plan, the Code of Conduct, the pan-European ROPA/DIPA.

The checklist below defines the minimum elements to be described by a new potential Consortium professional member as part of their application. Currently it includes (but is not limited) the following elements:

- ✓ The type of institution
- ✓ Main motive or incentive for joining (using the Public Value Assessment Tool, PLUTO²²)
- ✓ Explicit goals for joining the data Consortium
- ✓ Defined questions/use cases planned to be used in the enquiry of datasets
- ✓ Specific success measures such as key performance indicators for any specific project or enquiry
- ✓ Main areas of expertise
- ✓ Pathways to managing confidentiality (i.e. case numbers and analysis suppression for rare cases)
- ✓ Capacity of active involvement in the Consortium governance at a technical, clinical, administrative, and/or research ethics levels
- ✓ Submitting a report answering the questions outlined in the Managing institutional differences section (see D4.6 on how this has been done for existing Consortium members).

²² Public Value Assessment Tool (PLUTO) <https://pluto.univie.ac.at/>

The Consortium will use an API to provide secure access to disparate data systems and data formats. Access to the data ecosystem via the API will be permission-based with different levels of access. This checklist is applicable to professional users, may be adapted in time, and it sits separately to the evaluation process for individual patient users – which is to be defined by a different deliverable.

13.3. Decision process

For professional members who apply to join the Consortium, there will be a decision process evaluating at minimum the public value of the member’s research goals (using PLUTO), their status quo, gaps and differences between national ecosystems, and a definition of steps to be taken towards alignment to the pan-European ecosystems’ requirements (see D4.6. as an example of a previous such exercise).

The decision on approving membership and level of access will be made by the CfC on the basis of an application outlining the requirements detailed above and a report answering questions related to potential institutional differences. Decisions regarding the initial approval, level of user access, subsequent amendments to the user categories, and removal of user access will have to be approved by a majority of the STRONG-AYA CfC, after consultation with stakeholders and ad-hoc experts. The process of application and decision is summarised in Figure 2 below.

Figure 3: Journey of a potential member from the time of application to the use of the ecosystem infrastructure for federated analyses. Potential member fills in the application following internal evaluation of capacity and local ethical/governance processes; ; these are then checked by the Consortium CfC. Following checks, the new member is approved and their user access level defined. At this point they can provide retrospective data or collect new data to be contributed to the federated learning and analysis ecosystem (commensurate to local ethical approvals and GDPR) and they can request for use cases to be applied to data present in the ecosystem (subject to CfC review).

While the application process to become part of the Consortium requires a certain level of preparatory work on behalf of the potential partner, the benefits of being part of a data ecosystem are substantial. Through joining the pan-European ecosystem, provided the motives and incentives are judged as suitable by criteria laid down and regularly reviewed by the CfC, partners receive development support, access to reports and opportunities to develop new algorithms and improve the clinical and research work done in the benefit of AYA care. This currently free of charge - at no cost to the potential member, other than becoming part of future funding opportunities to support the sustainability of the ecosystem.

13.4. Management of user access and usage

This section offers definitions of minimum rules for access to the data ecosystem with levels of user access as well as ground rules to be followed by all Consortium members. During the decision making process each

new stakeholder will be assigned a ‘user category’ which defines their level of ‘user access’ to a range of data-driven learning that can be accessed within the STRONG-AYA ecosystem.

Consistent with the model of the Personal Health Train described on page 7 of this document, data stations are always under the control of the institution. The technical blueprint details how these are protected within the STRONG-AYA guidelines, but ultimately they are safeguarded by the local data protection measures. No one external to the member institution should ever have any rights or permissions to this. The levels of user access refer to the ‘tracks’ and ‘trains’ that provide the analytic and learning capability between these data stations. The levels of access will be:

- **Administrative:** view and edit rights to the backend of the data ecosystem and API
Medical Data Works (MDW) will be the only actors with Administrative access to the backend of the infrastructure. They will NOT have the ability to post epidemiological questions or formulate statistical hypotheses – their role is to manage and maintain the federated learning ecosystem.
- **Local administrative:** view and edit rights to the institutional data station
This level will be reserved for specific individuals of given consortium members who maintain and manage the data stations locally. They are expected to have specific data access approvals within their own institutions. They will be able to generate the necessary authentication keys of the data station, enable appropriate end-to-end encryption (i.e. data station-to-backend), and will require individual level access to the local data station for maintenance purposes. They will NOT have the ability to post epidemiological questions or formulate statistical hypotheses.
- **Full access:** complete view rights of content but without ability to edit
This level will be reserved for consortium members and their affiliates under the same institutional membership of the consortium. They will be able to look up descriptive statistics, post epidemiological questions and formulate statistical hypotheses that can be answered with the available data via the user interface. They will NOT have access to individual data stations nor can they post questions which have not yet been validated by the consortium members.
- **Partial access:** view rights relevant to approved stakeholders without consortium membership
These members will have restricted access to descriptive statistics but not to the same level as members with full research rights. For example, a pharmaceutical company might be allowed restricted access to descriptive statistics but not to epidemiological modelling. This would be an access level applicable to patients as well.
- **Observational access:** view rights to insights produced by the Consortium, but without access to data – generally reserved for the wider public.

This is the lowest level of access to descriptive statistics only and without access to interactions with the user interface. What the public is allowed to view will be reviewed by the Consortium members and is subject to local approvals of a specific user, and review of bona fide incentives (e.g. patient who has given consent to take part in the study or researcher in a specific institution).

Table 1 below defines the levels of user access to the pan-European data ecosystem, as they will be evaluated by the CfC members:

Table 1: Potential levels of user access according to: application process, membership status, type and expertise of potential partner.

Type of partner	Maximum level of access if Consortium member	Incentive and Expertise	Member application approved (Consortium Data protection agreement & Medical Data Works Infrastructure agreement signed)		Level of access		
			Yes	No	Consortium membership	Approved member	Non-member
Administrative	Reserved for Medical Data Works alone - Access to infrastructure backend for maintenance, without approval to submit or run queries						Not applicable
Local administrative	Reserved for local maintenance in Consortium member institutions, without approval to submit or run queries						
Clinical care (e.g. hospital)		Clinical care of patients			Full access		
Research (e.g. university epidemiology department)		Data analysis, clinical research			Partial access		
Policy maker (e.g. local health authority)		Policy and commissioning			Observational access		
Charity (e.g. patient advocacy group)		Supportive care and advocacy					
Private company (e.g. pharmaceutical industry)		Data analysis, clinical research					
Patient or carer		Personal interest					
Insurance company		Budgeting and financing					

Administrative users are a special category. They are either on the part of MDW, who will have access to the backend of the infrastructure for maintenance purposes or on the part of local (hospital or university) administration, whereby specific individuals in the local data stations will have access to the backend of the data repository, for maintenance purposes. None of the users in these roles will have the ability to perform analyses or submit use cases – their access is only for system maintenance and management.

For all other types of users, at the local level and across STRONG-AYA we will develop access and control protocols to block some information reaching some stakeholders. This will also be subject to the signing of the Data protection and Infrastructure user agreements. For example, pharmaceutical industry or medical devices companies may not be permitted to develop queries/models involving drugs administered or procedures carried out without that request being considered by the Consortium as a whole and data that is used for any such analyses being limited according to national ethical and regulatory frameworks. For instance, data on ethnicity cannot be utilised by law in France, so analyses of it may not be acceptable to be viewed by French participants.

Another example, is where the Consortium may approve certain users affiliated to a research institution as having a “research” profile, following bona fide checks. That will enable them to perform comparative effectiveness analyses and generate epidemiological models for health outcomes research (but strictly not for clinical decision-making). They can receive either full access if they answer all relevant points in the application and become a member of the Consortium, or maintain ‘observational’ access if they do not wish to undergo the application process. However, their incentives for accessing the platform and its outputs will still be vetted by the Consortium.

Alternatively, the Consortium may define other users as having a “carer” (or “policy maker”) profile. They are at maximum only permitted and able to enquire into aggregated global statistics of specifically AYA-related healthcare utilization disparities and values-centered outcomes. Policy makers who become members of the Consortium and have a defined project specific to the data ecosystem may be granted ‘full access’, but a member of the public enquiring for personal interest may only be offered ‘observational’ access. Importantly, there may also be a “patient” profile that allows the person to contribute their own PROs data, track their personal outcomes over time (through a portal in their local healthcare/hospital system), and overlay those on top of broad overall statistics of similar others and/or a

Europe-wide AYAs cancer population. In such cases, they can opt into becoming a member to be offered 'partial' access to the ecosystem. The means and methods of creating the patient profiles remain to be defined and co-created with AYA communities within other deliverables.

A special case is that of for-profit users. We identify two cases – that of pharmaceutical clinical research companies, which generally may have partial access, but may be upgraded to full access provided they become members of the Consortium through the routes detailed above, but with limitations on the incentives, and the type of queries they may submit. Insurance companies and other similar for-profit businesses cannot be granted more than partial access, hence they will be able to access the outcomes of pre-approved analyses.

A set of ground rules is set out below for all current and prospective users of the ecosystem, irrespective of their level of access:

- Wherever possible, it is encouraged and preferred for new Consortium members to be able to contribute their own datasets to the data ecosystem infrastructure. Active discussions with the Consortium research, informatics, and technical teams are encouraged for the structuring of data on agreed standards, improving (when necessary) or updating their own systems, and ensuring local training in the adoption and use of the API.
- The list of initially authorized purposes for the use of STRONG-AYA infrastructure is limited to education and research. Any other use will need to be discussed and approved by all WPs. This will be a technical, scientific, and ethics discussion that will involve all stakeholders, including patients. The list of additional authorized purposes will be then submitted to data contributors for approval.
- STRONG-AYA implements a “decentralized databases” approach, meaning that patient data will not leave secured repositories belonging to the institution that prepared the data. That is, no individual-level data, even if it is anonymized, shall be allowed to be transferred from one institution to another. Instead, the analysis will be sent out to disparate databases, and only the locally aggregated results (e.g. statistical summaries) will be combined at a central location, to achieve global statistical results, summarizing all datasets.
- While abiding by the open science principles, the privacy-preserving aspect of the STRONG-AYA dictates that the infrastructure will not be open access. It means that users will need to apply for permission, verified and authorized. An initial list of categories of eligible users such researcher, clinician, patient, decision-maker have been defined above. Users will have to ratify the STRONG-AYA Terms of Use.
- To maintain its credibility towards data holders the STRONG-AYA Consortium may need to monitor the purposes of the actual use of its tools by the users. Users will ratify the Terms of Use which is a minimal safeguard.
- The Consortium will request all active member users to submit periodically evidence of their *bona fide* use of the tools. This could be applicable to researchers who could, for example provide their research publications. This requires development of systems for other type of users, such clinicians – for example, healthcare professionals (who have professional and nationally legally enforced codes of conduct) may have to provide regular testimony (through automated alerts alongside identity checks and evidence that the response is from a 'human') of their adherence to specific regulations. How this will be set up separately for professional versus patient users is in discussion within the Consortium and will be the subject of future deliverables.
- All users will be encouraged and facilitated to report concerns about wrongdoing via the STRONG-AYA web interface, in an open supportive system. To become part of the Consortium a requirement is that each member/institution will have their own complaints procedure which will be checked as part of the PLUTO risk assessment tool. However, we will ensure the system allows for additional

concerns within the Consortium to be reported and resolved in a timely manner with appropriate replies to stakeholders.

- Partners must agree upon a balance between data utilization, data security, and preferences of the data providers. However, work to make the data analyses useful to others beyond the initial Consortium is vital to sustainability, so this needs to be subject to further work across the STRONG-AYA ecosystem as it grows and this document will be updated accordingly.
- In order to ensure the sustainability of the ecosystem infrastructure, through user access management and monitoring, Consortium members will be required to contribute and collaborate on ongoing funding initiatives for the ongoing use and maintenance of the system.
- While currently access to these services is free of charge, in the future, as the consortium grows and expands access to the eco-system infrastructure may develop into a subscription-type model.

13.5. Resolution of disputes and ambiguous situations

Disputes, complaints or ambiguous situations at local levels are expected to be resolved using the policies and processes specific to each institution as identified through PLUTO.

At the Consortium level, STRONG-AYA, where reasonable, will employ a bottom-up approach to adjudicate disputes or ambiguous situations (Figure 3). These may relate to decisions around the joining and membership to the data ecosystem and Consortium, concerns related to a new use case or research methods from any stakeholder (professional or patient). Any disputes arising between STRONG-AYA Consortium partners should be solved amicably and respectfully.

Ambiguities on any given criteria to establish thresholds of access or how rules and standards of operation are applied, will be discussed at the level of specific WP with the help of the work package leads and the Project Coordinator. If unresolved, the Project Coordinator will escalate the issue to the CfC (specifically the Coordinator and the Scientific Coordinator) who will use mediation, expert and referent powers to objectively aim to resolve the issue. If the ambiguous situations or disputes cannot be resolved at this level, the Coordinator may appoint a dispute resolution panel or opt to refer the issue to the General Assembly for wider consultation if needed.

If a partner wishes to complain about other partners in the Consortium, the complaint should be documented in writing. Such a complaint will be addressed to the CfC (Coordinator and the Scientific Coordinator) and the Project Coordinator in the first instance. If a complaint resolution panel cannot resolve the issue, the General Assembly will be convened and will vote on a resolution to reach a binding solution.

Figure 4: Process of dispute and complaint resolution within the STRONG-AYA Consortium

13.6. Submission of use cases

The STRONG-AYA Consortium has developed an initial priority list of how the data within the ecosystem infrastructure can be used by stakeholders for research and education purposes. This priority list can be seen as ‘research questions’ or ‘database queries’ or, as they will be referred to henceforth, ‘use cases’. These can only be submitted by Consortium members with full or partial user level access (see Figure 4 for a depiction of the process).

Figure 5: Process of submitting and approving new Use cases by Consortium members

The current list of use cases has been developed as a list of key questions, which could be answered by analysing data within each institution, aligned to the motives, goals, and performance indicators of the STRONG-AYA pan-European ecosystem as a whole and those of each of its members (local and national ecosystems). Consistent with the principles of standardisation and patient benefit, the use cases are aligned to the COS defined in WP1 (see D1.2) and they have been further defined and prioritised in collaboration with service users (patients and carers), healthcare professionals, researchers, health service managers, and policy makers (see D4.8). It is envisaged that this list of use cases is dynamic and will evolve over time. Consequently, here we set the rules for the development and submission of new use cases to the Consortium.

An approved member of the Consortium can choose to submit a use case to be reviewed by the CfC (for an example of how the initial use cases have been defined, see D4.8). The criteria these will be evaluated against are:

- **Demonstrable clinical benefit:** the use cases need to lead directly or imminently (within maximum 5 years) to improvement in clinical or psychosocial care.
- **Demonstrable co-design with relevant stakeholders:** members need to describe the process through which the use cases were identified, formulated, and prioritised with all stakeholders involved (patient groups, leads or members of other work packages, researchers, policy makers etc.).
- **Description of legal and ethical considerations:** use cases submitted for review should include an assessment of legal and ethical risks and mitigations procedures from local ethics/governance bodies and consistent with GDPR.
- **Description of administrative, technical, research, and clinical capability:** once a use case is submitted and approved it will produce an output which can be used by the member(s) of the Consortium. The implications of a given insight need to be assessed and reassurance offered that

the Consortium member(s) have the capacity to use the insight for patient benefit and prevent any unintended harm.

- **Plans for growth:** as part of the process of submitting a use case for review, Consortium members need to demonstrate the practical steps of how the use case will lead logically and in a timely manner to patient benefit, for themselves and/or other Consortium members, with associated KPIs.

14. Rules on using the ecosystem for federated learning and analytics

Once a Consortium partner has defined their local governance model, set up or upgraded their capabilities (technical, administrative, etc) to meet the standards of the Consortium, have had their use cases approved, and have implemented the API, they are ready to use the ecosystem for FL and analytics. This action is led by its own specifications and rules defined below.

14.1. Active contribution to the data ecosystem

New and existing partners are expected to contribute to the data ecosystem with their own datasets, which will support the sustainability and continuous development of the ecosystem. Honoring the principle of Standardisation defined earlier means that partners will need to identify ways to improve the structuring of their existing data and implement these improvements in new data collected.

To achieve this, partners and their local investigators may want to use metadata (information about data such as its origin, meaning, measuring scales, location, timing of collection, limits on storage duration, etc.) which will support the use of algorithms for federated analytics. While the STRONG-AYA commits to offering the tools and data science support to develop this, the uptake of local investigators is crucial to the understanding of data coding and labelling subtleties.

There is an expectation of differences in the labelling and formatting of datasets between local and national ecosystems. The Consortium welcomes differing data structures, as long as it can be joined up by metadata making it possible to pursue federated learning and analytics across the ecosystem. To assess internally whether active contribution is possible, each Consortium member needs to self-evaluate whether they can meet certain expectations (for more details, see D3.1. Data management plan and D3.3. Technical Blueprint), namely:

- Each Consortium member is expected to have a range of existing data already collected or being collected, covering PROs, clinical and service use data with relevance to AYAs with cancer. Capacity to provide metadata on these is necessary.
- The existing data will be associated with their own data collection workflows and data management practices characteristic to each institution, independent from STRONG-AYA, which can be transparently described.
- It can be expected that any new joining partners as well as existing ones will have a suitable local electronic patient record and a derived clinical database.
- Each centre has an existing (or at minimum in advanced development) database held in a secure research environment suitable for special category STRONG-AYA data. This will be used for the hosting of data locally, running local computations, and for the storage of partial summaries to integrate into the Consortium-wide statistical model as part of the federated learning process;
- Each joining partner needs to provide the metadata of the data they will be providing for the federated learning ecosystem to ensure and maintain the interpretability and interoperability of the system.

14.2. Abiding by the technical standards

The Technical Blueprint (D3.3.) details the technical requirements, the plan to leverage existing expertise, and then provide support to extend and improve local systems. The Consortium will provide support for partners to follow standards for the management of datasets to ensure data security, integrity and privacy preservation. STRONG-AYA promotes, encourages and empowers autonomy, flexibility and sustainability at the partner level. Each institution's contribution to the COS dataset in STRONG-AYA will remain fully controlled, and managed locally, by the leading investigator representing that institution. The technical teams of each partner institution in the Consortium must strive to improve their own datasets and their management with agreed, consistent system upgrades. The system needs to be able to use the APIs for federating data which will be programmed centrally (following use case approval) by members of the CfC following the principles and standards of the Consortium's governance model (Section 3). As the goals and objectives of the Consortium grow or additional partners join the Consortium, changes will need to be made and a clear change-management process will be further outlined within this dynamic report.

14.3. Privacy preservation

The STRONG-AYA Consortium is dedicated to the concept of 'privacy-by-design'. No data will be exported locally from where it has permissions to be held. Only authorised staff of a given institution are allowed access to the line-by-line data inside their data station. No one outside of that institution will be given access to this. Any remote access to the information (anonymised or pseudonymised) stored in a specific institution is completely forbidden.

However, each partner will be able to see the output of analyses that includes the data they have contributed, if they had been granted access to the layer of the ecosystem website holding those outputs. For example, patients may be able to see their own personal line-by-line Strong-AYA data (through a portal into their local Electronic Health Care records), but not the line-by-line data of others. However, they may be able to see comparative summaries of their own data against summaries of similar data of other similar patients (e.g. they may be able to see their reported PROs data versus average responses of other people with the same diagnosis).

Data relevant to the federated system will not be accessed by third parties without explicit, unanimous approval by all members of the Consortium and without explicit consent from patients contributing data to the Consortium. Protection from data breaches is ensured through a set of robust penetration tests – a report is available from the CfC upon request. Protection from data leakages is ensured through the local cybersecurity standards each institution has to follow, commensurate with the requirements set out in the Technical Blueprint and Data management plan. STRONG-AYA encourages partners to ensure the availability of a compensation fund, in the unlikely event they become a victim of cybersecurity attacks.

Data will not be used for the purposes of identifying patients or attempting to identify patients in any circumstances. Failure to follow this rule will result in immediate and permanent removal from access to the Consortium.

Any data breaches will be investigated using local data protection processes and by the CfC commensurate with the Data protection agreement.

14.4. Supporting interpretability and interoperability

A large part of work pursued by the STRONG-AYA pan-European ecosystem focused on ensuring the interpretability and interoperability of data at cross-national level through adherence to FAIR principles. This

was done through the development of the WP1 COS and use of metadata. The COS is an example of alignment of the data collected under the same definitions in various nations and institutions. This way, a common language is ensured as standardised, more homogeneous information can be collected and provided at local levels, which insures interoperability – any partner will be able to use the data collected with a clear knowledge of what it represents.

The use of metadata locally and across the consortium also ensures the interoperability of the data infrastructures. For example, haemoglobin may be measured across all participating countries. Metadata related to this data point in each institution will contain information of the measuring units in which it is represented (e.g. grams per decilitre of blood or grams per litre). While all these units of measurement are eligible and acceptable to be shared without a need for additional transformations, metadata associated with the variable is necessary to ensure algorithms (APIs) can be programmed to run transformations automatically and that the output can be easily interpreted by the user. Another example is that of specific interpretations of less known variables – such as nicotine exposure. This can be encoded as ‘smoking cigarettes’ or ‘chewing tobacco’ as lower level sub-classes of nicotine exposure but it can also be accompanied by quantity specifications such as number of pack/years of consumption. Similarly, one may define a higher level class of ‘T4’ for tumour staging, with T4a and T4b as sub-classes. In this case, searching for ‘T4’ will return all participants with T4, T4a, and T4b, whereas searching for T4a will only return these specific participants with a T4a. The programming within the API will be based on the embedded hierarchical relationships between variables.

To enhance the re-usability of local datasets the federated queries (developed on the basis of use cases) will convert specific data labels provided via metadata into generic (i.e. schema-independent RDF objects) and then adding study-specific annotations. Thus, consistency in the metadata shared by each partner is necessary to ensure the system is interoperable and a correct interpretation of the COS data and insights. While the COS has already been defined, there is some flexibility whereby new outcomes of interest may be added if associated with a clear rationale and provided their measurement does not raise ethical concerns such as discrimination. These aspects will be evaluated by CfC in collaboration with WP2.

In the event that a prospective partner is only collecting a specific, niche type of data without plans of expanding this in volume or scope, this will influence their ability to make the Consortium successful. Consequently, when the type of existing or planned to be collected data is limited in availability (e.g. very rare tumour types) partners will need to provide information on future data collection plans and/or growth trajectories for data sets as a way of helping themselves and CfC determine institutional capacity.

The Consortium appreciates the time and effort necessary for these exercises if this work is not already in place as part of the local data management system, and is committed to providing support when necessary and feasible. Differing precise types of data should not be a roadblock to a successful data ecosystem and Consortium, but there needs to be a recognition that the absence of such information may limit the long-term operation of the Consortium and will limit the ability to derive new insights via federated learning and ultimately deliver on shared goals and incentives.

14.5. Tracking success with KPIs

As part of the application process, potential new members will need to define and provide a breakdown of key performance indicators (KPIs) associated with their incentives and goals (see D5.2 as an example). This is also a requirement for ongoing members, hence KPIs will be characteristic of each new project a partner develops and will related directly to the existing and new use cases submitted for CfC review. The data insights accessed via the federated system and subsequent clinical or research findings will be tracked in line

with agreed KPIs, which will be dependent on the build of the API (i.e. the algorithms sent through the federated ecosystem to produce summary statistics).

14.6. Using the infrastructure

For the use of the STRONG-AYA infrastructure members need to:

- Abide by a purpose that is within the list of acceptable authorized purposes for use (e.g. education or research) and consistent with the limitations of local registers. Any purpose not approved initially should be discussed and approved with the Consortium and data providers.
- A disclaimer will be available on all visible part of the STRONG-AYA infrastructure stating that the available tools should be used only for research or education purposes. Concrete examples will be made available.
- Follow the recommendations and training provided on how we are legally permitted and have agreement to use the system for the different purposes such for patient information, research, etc.
- Users will be made aware of the limitations of using AI solution and the challenges to incorporate AI in the patient-doctor interactions.
- All Consortium members need to raise user awareness about the risk of overreliance on the system. Users should take the time to understand and to challenge the outcomes from the system before implementing them especially in clinical setting. Clinicians should make first their own diagnosis and then compare it with the output from the system.

Training materials, disclaimers, and output descriptions on the STRONG-AYA web interface will be adapted to the type of users – healthcare professionals or patients – in conjunction with other deliverables. Below (Table 2) we identified a list of potential risks associated with the use of a special category data ecosystem and some of the ways in which these risks will be mitigated by STRONG-AYA. This list is not exhaustive and additional risks will be added as they are identified. Importantly, while some the levels of risks will be different for patients versus professional users, here we offer a generic overview. For additional information please refer to the Code of Conduct (D2.2) and Grant agreement.

Risks	Mitigation rules
Risks related to patient participants	
Patient re-identification	
<p>Many people living with a rare disease may be easier to re-identify due to the low number of other individuals in the world with the same variants of a specific rare disease.</p> <p>In the case of extreme rare events re-identification can take place through the crossing of data from the same patients from different but accessible sources.</p> <p>Attempting data queries of rare events with minor changes in settings/rules of data searches can lead to the attributes of participants being inferred.</p>	<p>There will be an ongoing effort to seek data to achieve greater volumes of diagnoses for people with rare diseases.</p> <p>The software automatically excludes any computations on 10 or fewer subjects in any given data station.</p> <p>No analyses will be permitted internationally if data cells fall under the agreed data suppression thresholds (such as 10 cases per cell).</p> <p>These restrictions will apply both for absolute data quantity but also for the amount of new data added</p>

	<p>to the ecosystem since the last analysis by any one API.</p> <p>This prevents analyses and re-analyses inadvertently providing identifiable information or participant attributes to be inferred.</p>
Risks	Mitigation rules
Patient withdrawal from study	
<p>Patients may wish to withdraw their contribution to STRONG-AYA following the pseudonymisation of data.</p>	<p>Being able to withdraw consent is a right conferred by GDPR. As the initial pseudonymisation of data is done locally by each institution, and the request of withdrawal will be directed at that institution, such cases will be dealt with locally.</p> <p>Consortium members managing local data station are expected to have the means (within the limits of their own governance systems) to manage changes in consent status and re-identify participants, if necessary, by accessing their own data store separate from the pseudonymised dataset used for federated learning.</p>
Patient participants do not engage or do not adhere to survey completions	
<p>Lack of patient engagement and adherence to survey completion is common in PRO research studies.</p>	<p>To mitigate this, patient advice will be sought in the development of tools and outcomes to be collected through the STRONG-AYA Patient Advisory Board. They will ensure materials are visually engaging, sufficiently informative and aligned to patient needs to motivate the completion of the questionnaire and to ensure retention. Personalized feedback is envisaged to motivate patients to continue participation. Guidance and helpdesks will be available.</p>
Discrimination or other uses not in the interest of the patients (harmful use)	
<p>Potential queries in the API may lead to discriminatory conclusions, which could endanger patient safety.</p> <p>The use and integration of AI/big data solution into medical practice brings the challenge of preserving patient rights and interests, while still making full use of innovation.</p>	<p>Potential queries of variables within the ecosystem which might lead to biased discriminatory conclusions will be limited through the design of the system. However, it is difficult to envisage all the ways in which a query might lead to discrimination without limiting the use of psychosocial variables. Users of the system will be able to flag particular queries or variables as potentially discriminatory and offer a description of this concern. This will enable STRONG-AYA to improve the system over time.</p> <p>Users of the STRONG-AYA research infrastructure should employ it only for the benefit of the patient (on the basis of <i>bona fide</i> research for the improvement of patient survival and quality of life). This is ensured through the tracking of API usage and</p>

	<p>its alignment with pre-defined KPIs, use cases, and goals.</p> <p><u>Users should not use the infrastructure for potentially harmful use that could lead to any type of discrimination or endanger patient’s wellbeing. Any such actions will lead to the removal of the partner from the Consortium.</u></p>
Risks	Mitigation rules
Distressing conclusions	
<p>Data generated by the STRONG-AYA infrastructure may require strength in the patient-doctor relationship, such as different cancer outcomes between nations and centres. The infrastructure could provide information to a health care professional or a patient which requires discussion and explanation to manage any distress.</p>	<p>Appropriate training and guidance will be provided to all users of the system for how insights generated should be interpreted or be communicated to a patient (if not the user).</p> <p>The STRONG-AYA infrastructure will not be a route to specific clinical advice. However, for those who may have particular questions, healthcare professional contact information will be made available for patients to discuss potentially distressing findings.</p> <p>Technical feedback can be provided by IKNL and UNIMAAS as members of a CfC. The interpretation of analyses completed by the APIs will be joined by their purpose, appropriate FAQs, information on the limitations or common misconceptions about the findings.</p> <p>Appropriate disclaimers will be put in place where resulting insights might be distressing to a user, especially in the case of patient/carers. However, a bespoke set of training, output descriptions and disclaimers will be designed for professional versus patient users.</p>
Risks to professional members of the Consortium	
Differences in legal, ethical, or technical standards in local ecosystems of Consortium members	
<p>Difficulties in creating the legal entity and in developing a viable operating plan for the pan-EU ecosystem due to lack of alignment of national ecosystems operating models.</p>	<p>This will be mitigated according to the section on Managing institutional gaps and differences. There will be an expectation of alignment to local governance/ethical standards and processes as well as GDPR from each consortium member.</p>

Risks	Mitigation Rules
System overreliance for clinical decision making	
<p>It may be difficult to prevent clinicians from using the system to support their clinical decision-making. This introduces is a risk of overreliance on the system.</p> <p>All final clinical decisions will remain with the clinician, but they may be influenced by the outputs from the system (e.g. quality of life data being used in clinical practice).</p>	<p>The STRONG-AYA research infrastructure is devoted to research and educational uses and this rule needs to be followed by all partners.</p> <p>The Consortium will assess, on a case-by-case basis, how the results could be used for clinical decision-making (within the portals to STRONG-AYA and data in local Electronic Health Records) and which limitations are therefore applicable.</p> <p>The purpose of making a specific query in the API will need to be declared by each user at point of use.</p> <p>Appropriate training and guidance will be provided to new users of the system and a feedback procedure from users be made available so that users can challenge outputs if needed. Outputs will include appropriate descriptions and disclaimers commensurate with the type of user that may view them. Users will also be able to contact the STRONG-AYA helpdesk or the local investigators for additional questions and clarifications.</p>
Queries outside scope	
<p>This relates to queries, algorithms, or use cases placed within the API for processing, but outside of the scope of the Consortium and its goals.</p>	<p>Data that is collected and available to be queried will always be within the disease area of focus.</p> <p>New queries and use cases are permitted only after due process, considering ethical, motivation-based and wider scientific conditions.</p> <p>Any query, algorithm, or use case submitted via the API which is not aligned to a pre-defined KPI, goal, and approved by the CfC will return an error message.</p>
Inconclusive results	
<p>The user asks wrongly formulated questions which results in inconclusive findings, which could still be applied in clinical practice, hence putting patient safety at risk.</p>	<p>There is need for user education and awareness on how to formulate use cases and how to use variables within the system to answer these.</p> <p>Appropriate training and guidance will be provided to new users of the system and a feedback procedure from users be made available so that users can challenge outputs if needed.</p> <p>Appropriate disclaimers will be available for the various outputs, tailored to the type of users.</p> <p>Training, guidance and disclaimers are developed by Consortium members as part of other deliverables.</p>
Failure of the technical system due to external attacks on infrastructure	

<p>Given the technical nature of FL ecosystems cyber-attacks on infrastructure are a risk in the form of data poisoning; eavesdropping; model poisoning; decommissioning of the server; decommissioning of the institutional data point; penetration of the central service; privacy reversion.</p>	<p>These aspects have been considered in detail by the STRONG-AYA technical leads and safeguards are in place as detailed across multiple documents including ROPA/DPIA, Technical Blueprint, etc. Appropriate and robust system penetration testing has been pursued and the report, which identified minimal such risks, is available upon request.</p> <p>Over and above safeguarding at the umbrella ecosystem level, local investigators must follow institutional access and data control policies (multi-factor authentication, strong passwords, not sharing passwords, not giving access to unwanted persons; people interacting with STRONG AYA must be staff who are reporting their actions to the PI). There are measures in place to restrict access to the central server to the minimum number of necessary personnel. Mitigation is by design and encryption – by exchanging only summaries or models and by encrypting telecommunications it’s unfeasible to re-identify a person.</p>
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Table 3. Risks and mitigation rules

14.7. Intellectual property guidelines

All members of the Consortium agree to share intellectual properly and give credit to the Consortium as a whole. If an institution has a pre-existing internal intellectual properly policy, that policy needs to be communicated if different from the statement above. The local institutional policies of the Consortium member will be applied for any discoveries made using data outside of the Consortium’s dataset (i.e. PRO or clinical data available in an institution that is not made available/shared with the Consortium).

14.8. Sharing of benefits - Communication and dissemination of outputs

All parts of the work conducted by the Consortium is expected to be reviewed by the CfC and Project Coordinator. They are expected to refine work (such as the COS, Data management plan or this present report), update it, ensure that there is a clear channel to communicate it to partners (i.e. the project Microsoft Teams shared drive and email communications) and to oversee how this work is implemented. Other communication methods will include internal information exchange in pre-defined project meetings, newsletters, and summaries of newly delivered reports to all partners. All and any outputs connected to the data and information (i.e. including images, new ways of working, policy outreach activities etc.) produced within the STRONG-AYA ecosystem should credit the Consortium as a whole.

15. The operational plan

	Limitations	Facilitators	Risks	Mitigations	Methods	Metrics
National Ecosystem Setup	True national data is limited to Netherlands, progressing in the UK and France, but limited in Italy and Poland	National leadership in AYA and data in Netherlands, UK, France, and Italy, with developing AYA culture and leadership in Poland	Delayed receipt of national-reach data, in particular in PROs.	Increased data policy engagement in 2024-25	Small group meetings and proposed policy fora (See D4.4)	National data agreements in UK and France 01-Jul-2025
Technology and Data Integration	Delays in CoS mean delays in testing data integration in Federated systems	Portal installation proceeding strongly in all local systems	Late agreement of dataset delays publications	Push to finalise CoS dataset by WP1 with all partners	Consensus meetings	CoS agreed 20-Dec-2024
Governance and Compliance	Delayed governance approvals in some nations	National and AYA cancer data leadership	Limited dataset from some nations, within European Umbrella ecosystem	Compensatory data volumes from other centres	Policy engagement in each participating nation	Update report from each nation on policy engagement 01-Jul-2025
Stakeholder Involvement	Limited policy-maker engagement with project, therefore reliant upon data altruism	Other strong stakeholder engagement Strong links to AYA cancer policy frameworks where	Limited true national (population-based) data in STRONG-AYA analyses, in PROs particularly.	Engagement with population-based cancer registers	Joint meetings with national register data leads	Update report from each nation on policy engagement 01-Jul-2025

	rather than policy incentives Strong stakeholder engagement in all other groups	in place and strengthening in Italy and other nations due to JANE2(AYA)				
Continuous Monitoring and Control	Only been tested in dummy data so far, with strong results	Secure and ongoing strongly in other Vantage 6 systems led by MAASTRO	Unusual data security issue arises	Extensive experience in NKI and Maastro of rare dataset multi-nationals European data security	NA	NA

16. Re-auditing of rules and standards

This document, as well as the associated reports it is based upon, will undergo reviews, updates and refinement as the Consortium continues to grow and mature. Any feedback, suggestions, recommendations should in the first instance be addressed to the Project Coordinator who will then communicate these to the relevant WP leads and CfC members. Approved changes to this document or others will be communicated to all stakeholders to maintain accountability towards all users.

17. Commitments of Consortium and partners

Thus far this document laid out a range of rules and standards to be followed to resolve challenges that may be faced in the ecosystem at a pan-European level. The efficiency of the pan-European infrastructure cannot be ensured without alignment from each national (and institutional) ecosystem.

Consequently, all current and new partners commit to:

- Following the principles, rules, and standards laid out within this document
- Having confirmed review of other supporting documents mentioned above
- Maintaining European ethical standards and communicating promptly any local changes
- Ensuring and maintaining technical standards for data security, integrity, privacy as laid out in the Technical Blueprint and in adherence with local and/or national processes and regulations
- A common technology infrastructure, supporting secure telecommunications and web-based applications/computation algorithms
- A common data management structure with the use of metadata
- A common set of local standard technical operation rules and governance guidelines define who is allowed to learn what insight, from what data and for which legitimate purpose.

What we commit to do as a Consortium:

- **STRONG-AYA is about developing a process and a new way of working to share patient data safely and securely in addition to collecting data; it's not a traditional multi-center clinical trial.** As such, it may operate in ways that are unfamiliar to some and the Consortium is here to support centres to align to its standards and modes of working.
- **STRONG-AYA works in both an iterative and predictive manner.** Predictive projects are projects in which the three major constraints of the project (the scope, time and cost) are determined ahead of time not just at a high level, but in detail, and the project is split up into phases which can be either sequential or overlapping (e.g., clinical trial). In iterative projects, the scope is not determined ahead of time at a detailed level, but only for the first iteration or phase of the project. Once that phase is completed, the detailed scope of the next phase is worked out, and so on (e.g., technological development, UX design, etc.). In practice this means working with agility and responding to iterations of information on offer, in addition to a more linear predictive models.
- **STRONG-AYA encourages opportunities for growth but meets participating centres where they are, in terms of their constraints and challenges, in a supportive and pragmatic manner.** STRONG-AYA at its most ambitious offers the opportunity to develop a new process of treating AYAs with cancer. However, that does not mean that expectations and timelines are applied as an arbitrary standard across the Consortium. Consideration of local contexts is paramount and STRONG-AYA will meet each centre where their capabilities and capacities lie. The technical and legal infrastructure has been designed to handle different ways of structuring data, different electronic patient records, different laws etc. What works in one country may not work in another. However,

STRONG-AYA will also encourage growth and adaptation beyond the status quo. This is an opportunity to push beyond current practice and to do something innovative. This does not just apply to the development of new technology but also to learning from each other about what is possible.

- **STRONG-AYA offers pan-European expert guidance to local knowledge and empowerment.** STRONG-AYA brings together leading experts across disciplines that can help establish best practice and ensure pan-European operation across the Consortium. At the local level, PIs are empowered to find the people necessary to carry out the action of the project (hiring research nurse, IT/data managers/project managers, etc. as required) and to build the local relationships within and outside their institutions to collect the necessary data and create new ways of working.

18. Conclusion

This deliverable describes the actions to be fulfilled and rules and standards to be followed by ongoing and new members of the STRONG-AYA consortium and federated learning ecosystem.

The STRONG-AYA pan-European consortium has already undertaken important work which feeds into this deliverable, through literature reviews, a Delphi process, interviews, surveys, group, and one-to-one discussions. This work is presented within the following documents which should be read and implemented by all ongoing and new members of the consortium, and will be referred to throughout this report:

- Architecture of the ecosystem (D2.1)
- Code of conduct for members (D2.2)
- Data management plan (D3.1)
- Technical Blueprint (D3.3)
- Local operational plans (D4.6)
- Definition of use cases (D4.8)
- Core Outcome Set (D1.2)
- Key Performance indicators (D5.2)
- ROPA/DPIA
- Project Grant agreement.

As described within this report, our next steps refer to the setting up of the Committee for Coordination, implementing the processes for new member applications and submission of use of new cases, and communication and co-design with members of the patient advisory board. More specifically, future actions include:

Action	Deliverables	Timelines
Actions for the leadership team		
Define the Committee for Coordination (CfC)	D5.1 defines the steering committee members	Submitted May 2023
Agree on processes for resolution of disputes and ambiguities	D5.1 defines processes within the Consortium	Submitted May 2023
Develop and publish the STRONG-AYA Terms of Use (including details of monitoring processes of the actual ecosystem use)	Not applicable	Throughout the project
Develop and implement a system for reporting concerns	D5.1 defines processes within the Consortium. Each	Submitted May 2023

	national ecosystem has their own processes.	
Create a template for the periodical generation of evidence describing the use of the infrastructure (e.g. research publications, regular testimony through automated alerts, identity checks)	Task 3.6, D3.6	D3.6: 30 September 2024 T3.6: 10/2022-09/2027
Agree upon change-management processes (to adapt to new partners, support them, respond to changing ethical/technical standards internationally or locally)	Consortium agreement and Grant agreement	Throughout the project
Actions related to new member application and submission of new use cases		
Develop application pack template for new members (i.e. including templates for local capability and dataset/metadata availability)	Task 4.10	September 2027
Framework for evaluating new member applications (i.e. criteria and thresholds for accessing the ecosystem and the application programming interface)	Task 4.10	September 2027
Establish the template for the contribution with metadata (dataset structuring)	Tasks 3.5, 3.6, 3.9	September 2027
Determine and describe a standard for data structure	Tasks 3.5, 3.6, 3.9	September 2027
Agree on template for the submission of new use cases	Tasks 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5	September 2027
Agree on the framework to evaluate the submission of new cases (i.e. clinical benefit, demonstrable co-design, description of legal and ethical consideration, administrative, technical, research and clinical capability, plans for growth)	Tasks 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5	September 2027
Define a list of authorised purposes for the use of STRONG-AYA infrastructure and processes to submit additional authorised purposes to data contributors for approval	Data controllership agreement (i.e. legal document needed to start federated learning)	September 2024
Actions related to communication and co-design		
Define communication channels and processes between CfC and wider consortium members (for professionals)	Project handbook – through the Project manager and the annual reports on the ecosystem (D4.9, D4.10, D4.13, D.17)	Throughout the project
Define communication channels and processes between CfC and patient representatives	Via the Patient Advisory Board and D4.1	Not applicable
Involve patient representatives in the design and implementation of use cases and API (including the creation of patient profiles)	Tasks 1.2, 3.2, 3.7, 4.6 D1.1, D3.4, D3.5, D3.6, D3.8, D3.12, D3.13, D3.14	Throughout the project D1.1 submitted

Involvement of professionals in the design and implementation of the professional-facing profiles	Tasks 1.2, 3.2, 3.7. D1.1, D3.4, D3.5, D3.6, D3.8, D3.12, D3.13, D3.14	Throughout the project D1.1 submitted
Define how consortium members and users are informed both of the benefits and limits of tools developed by the Consortium, so they can customise their interactions with these tools	Task 4.6, D4.11 and D4.12	September 2025
Develop training materials on the use of the data ecosystem and API for members with various levels of user access (clinicians, patients, researchers, etc.).	Task 4.6, D4.1, D4.11	September 2025